

UZBEK CLASSICS ABOUT THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE

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Annotation. *This article includes the thinker, scholar, and one of the most mature figures of his time, Abu Rayhan Beruni and Abu Ali Ibn Sina, who introduced their views to science and revealed and fully elucidated the linguistic and non-linguistic principles of a number of sciences.*

Keywords: *linguistic letters, medicines, Saydana's work, descriptive, etymological, dialectological, physical sounds, speech sound, letter words-terms.*

Abu Rayhan al-Beruni (937-1048), an encyclopedic scholar from Khorezm known as Aliborona, is said to have created more than 150 works. These works belong to such dangerous fields as mathematics, phonetics, chemistry, astronomy, geography, medicine, literature, music, mathematics and natural sciences, and are valued as masterpieces of world science. The linguistic letters of Abu Rayhan Beruni are given in his work "Saydana". In this work, the great scholar not only describes how medicinal substances are called in several languages, but also points out the local naming of these substances in each language, that is, in each dialect. Hence, the author pays special attention to the question of the relationship between the subject and its name, which has been one of the most pressing problems of the science of language since ancient linguistics. Beruni also deals with poetry, creates works, and creates poetry himself. In Saydana, he cites examples from the poetry of a number of poets.

1. Abu Nurhan Beruni's views on linguistics in A.Nurmonov (Nang k, aig; used his work).

Beruni explains the names of medicinal substances in 29 chapters and 111 articles in the work. Each chapter is dedicated to one letter. He collects and interprets the names of plants, animals and medicines from more than 4,500 Arabic, Greek, Syriac, Persian, Khorezmian, Sogdian, Turkish and other languages.

Thus, the work "Saydana" is also valued as an explanatory dictionary of the names of medicinal substances. The author places the names of drugs in the play in the Arabic alphabet. If there are several words beginning with a letter, they are given based on the internal alphabet in that letter section. This dictionary has a special significance as an explanatory, translated, etymological and dialectological dictionary.

Our compatriot Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), known in Europe as Avicenna and glorified in the East as "Shaykhurrais", created a number of works in various fields, including linguistics. The encyclopedic scholar Ibn Sina: 1) "Kitab al-milh, fin-nahv" ("The book that is in the syntax of sharpness") 2) "Kitab lisonul arab" ("Book of the Arabic language") 3) In these works, the scholar was able to fully express himself as a highly spiritual, strong writer.

To date, four editions of *Asbobi Hudut al Huruf* are known: Cairo (2), Tbilisi Sodiun and Tashkent.

Professor A.Mahmudov and Professor K.Mahmudov analyzed and studied the works of the scholar in the Tashkent edition and gave their opinions.

This work consists of an introduction and six chapters. The source discusses the causes of sound and speech sounds, the anatomy of the throat and tongue, the peculiarities of the appearance of some Arabic sounds, speech sounds similar to these sounds, and the fact that sounds are heard in non-speech movements.

Ibn Sina rightly points out that the wave-like movement of air is the cause of the formation of sound. Specifically, speech sounds occur as a result of air being squeezed out of the articulation site.

He distinguishes between physical sounds and speech sounds. Physical sounds are called "savt", and speech sounds are called "letter". It is emphasized that both the physical sound and the speech sound are formed due to the undulating motion of the air.

Hence, the undulating motion of air in the formation of these sounds is common. At the same time, the peculiarity of this generality is that, unlike savts - physical sounds, certain members of speech are involved in the formation of letters - speech sounds. Hence, speech sounds occur through speech organs, directly in their presence.

Ibn Sina divided letters into speech sounds into vowels and consonants. Defines the number of vowels as three and the number of consonants as twenty-eight. Provides excellent information about consonants. In general, Ibn Sina's work in the field of phonetics, his ideas, especially his division of sounds into vowels and consonants, should be considered as a significant contribution to the development of world linguistics.²

REFERENCES:

1.A.Nurmonov. History of Uzbek linguistics. T., 2002. X Xomidov. Kirk, the story of five scholars. T., 1995.

2.E.Umarov. Grammar of the Starouzbek language. Mabani ul-lutat Mirzy Mexdixana. AKD, T., 1967. 3. Devonian lugatit turk I, II, III. T., 1960-1963. 10. Mahmud az Zamakhshari. Kozik phrases. T., 1992.

3.D.M.Nasilov. Linguistic views of Alishera Navai. V kn. History of lingvisticheskix ucheniy. Middle East. L., 1981. 12. History of lingvisticheskix ucheniy. Sredneveko

4.Khabiba,J.(2021). The Relationship Between a Person and His Personality. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 1(4), 48–50. Retrieved from <http://openaccessjournals.eu/index.php/ijdpp/article/view/205>

5.Jurabekova K. M. ROLE OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN INCREASING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 519-527.